

Effect of Addition of Moringa (*Moringa Oleifera L.*) Seed Flour on the Quality Characteristics of Mayonnaise

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Abstract— Mayonnaise is a semi solid oil-in-water emulsion product with high fat content. Fatty foods have oxidative properties with health related issues and there is a high demand for healthier and more nutritious foods. Moringa seed is a nutritious seed with high anti-oxidative properties. Therefore, this study evaluated the effect of moringa seed flour addition on the quality parameters of mayonnaise.

Moringa seed was locally procured and other ingredients (olive oil, egg, vinegar, salt, sugar) used in mayonnaise production were purchased locally. Moringa seed flour at 0, 1, 2 and 3% were added to the prepared mayonnaise samples while commercial mayonnaise sample served as control. The proximate composition (moisture, protein, fat, ash, crude fibre and carbohydrate content) of the moringa seed flour and mayonnaise samples were determined. The chemical composition (saponification value, acid value, iodine value, peroxide value and pH) of the produced mayonnaise and control were determined. Microbial analysis (bacteria and fungi count) were determined on the produced mayonnaise samples. Sensory evaluation (appearance, colour, taste, texture, overall acceptability) of the mayonnaise samples was equally carried out. Data obtained were subjected to Analysis of Variance and means separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test at 5% level of significance.

The moisture, protein, fat, ash, crude fibre and carbohydrate content of the moringa seed flour were 5.10, 3.83, 38.99, 28.62, 7.56 and 15.90%, respectively. The range of values obtained for the produced mayonnaise samples were 2.35% - 5.30, 0.14 - 0.42, 0.68 - 1.59, 54.47- 92.63 and 7.16-58.87% for moisture, protein, ash, fat and carbohydrate content. The corresponding values for the control were 4.37, 0.14, 1.80, 34.82 and 58.87%. The saponification, acid, iodine, peroxide and pH values for the produced mayonnaise ranged between 50.49 - 145.86 mgKOH/g oil, 1.68- 11.78 mgKOH/g oil, 50.52 - 80.52 g/100 g oil, 3.97- 23.97 meqO₂/kg oil, 5.09 - 5.68, while the corresponding value for the control were 196.35 mgKOH/g oil, 5.39 mgKOH/g oil, 112.47 g/100g oil, 7.17 meqO₂/kg oil and 3.40. The ranges of bacteria and fungi counts were 1x10² - 4x10² cfu/g and 2x10¹ - 8x10¹sfu/g respectively for produced mayonnaise samples. The mayonnaise sample with 1% moringa seed flour had 43.41% general acceptability.

This study has shown that mayonnaise produced with 1% moringa seed flour has better nutritional and sensory properties. Hence, moringa seed enhanced the nutritional value of mayonnaise.

Keywords— Moringa seed, proximate composition, Mayonnaise, Sensory evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Moringa oleifera (Syn. *M. ptrygosperma* Gaertn.) of the family *Moringaceae* is a small graceful tree with sparse foliage, often planted in compounds or used as hedges in northern part of Nigeria. It is a fast growing, aesthetically pleasing small tree (Kawo *et al.*, 2009). The specie characterized by long, drumstick shaped pods which contain seeds within the first year of growth (Ajar *et al.*, 2013). The tree is well known for its nutritional and medicinal values in many communities in the northern part of Nigeria (Kawo *et al.*, 2009). Olugbemi *et al.* (2010) reported that moringa is a good source of amino acids and vitamins. Abdulkarim *et al.*, 2005, have described the high levels of total proteins (383.0 standard deviation - SD=13.0g/kg dry matter), that turned out to be greater than important leguminous seeds with respect to human nutrition, with dry seeds usually containing 18 to 25% of protein, which nearly double cereals content. It also contains fiber, fats, minerals, proteins, and vitamins A, B, C and amino acids (Rockwood *et al.*, 2013; Thurber and Fahey, 2010; Mbikay, 2012; Nair and Varalakshmi, 2011; Satalangka *et al.*, 2013). The moringa pods are rich in lipids, fiber, non-structural carbohydrates, ash and protein. It also contain fatty acids like linoleic acid, oleic acid, palmitic acid and linolenic acid are also present (Rockwood *et al.*, 2013; Thurber and Fahey, 2010).

Mayonnaise is Oil-in-Water emulsion where egg proteins including lipoproteins act as emulsifiers. Mayonnaise emulsions are stabilized primarily through steric forces (Gaonkar *et al.*, 2010). Traditional mayonnaise should contain about 80% oil, according to the legislation, and its rheological properties depend on the oil content (Štern *et al.*, 2001; 2007). With the addition of modified starch, xanthan, β-glucan or other thickening agents, the oil content is substantially lower in low-energy light mayonnaises ((Lee, 2001; Vaikousi and Biliaderis, 2005).

The aim of this work was to investigate the effect of moringa seed flour addition on the quality parameters of mayonnaise.

The objectives are to:

- (i) determine the effect of moringa seed flour on the proximate and chemical composition of mayonnaise,

- (ii) determine the effect of moringa seed flour fortification on the microbial qualities of mayonnaise, and
- (iii) evaluate the sensory attributes of the mayonnaise as affected by moringa seed flour addition.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Moringa seed was obtained from Ganmo market, Ilorin. Olive oil, vinegar, salt; sugar and extreme mayonnaise were obtained from Shoprite superstore, Ilorin

Mayonnaise was produced using the following materials: olive oil, vinegar, salt, sugar, moringa seed flour at different percentages (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%)

Fig. 1: Flow diagram for the production of mayonnaise fortified with moringa seed flour

Table 1. Ingredients used in the preparation of mayonnaise fortified with moringa seed flour

Samples	Weight of oil used (g)	weight of moringa seed flour used (g)	Weight of mayonnaise produced (g)	Weight of acidifiers used (g)
A	183.2	0.00	205.1	5.25
B	137.4	2.20	145.2	5.25
C	91.6	4.41	104.7	5.25
D	45.8	6.61	83.5	5.25
E	183.2	0.00	205.1	4.58
F	137.4	2.20	145.2	4.58
G	91.6	4.41	104.7	4.58
H	45.8	6.61	83.5	4.58
I	183.2	0.00	205.1	4.79
J	137.4	2.20	145.2	4.79
K	91.6	4.41	104.7	4.79
L	45.8	6.61	83.5	4.79

Key:

A =Mayonnaise made with lemon juice, B = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, C = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, D = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, E = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar, F = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar+ 1% moringa seed flour, G = Mayonnaise made with vinegar + 2% moringa seed flour, H = Mayonnaise made with vinegar+ 3% moringa seed flour, I = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice, J = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, K = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, L = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour. Samples I-L were prepared using 2.5mls of lemon juice and 2.5mls of vinegar to get 5mls acidifier.

2.1 Proximate Analysis

2.1.1 Moisture content

An empty petri dish was dried in the oven for about 15 minutes and allowed to cool in a desiccator. Exactly 40 g of sample was weighed into a petri dish and placed in an oven at 40 °C for 10 minutes. It was then be put in a desiccator to cool down and reweighed.

This process was repeated until a constant weight was obtained. The percentage moisture content was then calculated as follows.

$$\text{Moisture content (wet basis \%)} = \frac{(B - C) - (D - C)}{A} \times 100 \quad (2.1)$$

where A = Initial (wet) weight of sample (g)

B = weight of petri dish +sample before oven drying (g)

C = weight of petri dish (g)

D = Weight of petri dish + dry sample after oven drying (g)

2.1.2 Protein content

This was determined using the micro Kjeldahl method (AOAC, 2010) as shown in Plate 3.2. Exactly 2.0 g of the sample was carefully weighed into a digestion flask; 5 g of copper sulphate pentahydrate, 10 g of sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and 25 cm³ was also added to the flask. The mixture was boiled until there was a colour changed from brown to brilliant green. The digest was diluted to 250 cm³ mark with distilled water after cooling. 5 cm³ of the digest was pipetted and delivered into Markham distillation apparatus. 10 cm³ of 1.25% sodium hydroxide was added and distilled. 5 cm³ of boric acid was put into a conical flask and the distillate was collected inside the conical flask. The green colour ammonium borate was titrated with 0.1 N HCl, the colour changed from green to blue to mark the end of titration and the

titre value was recorded. The percentage nitrogen was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ protein content} = 14 \times \frac{v}{100} \times 0.1 \times \frac{w}{100} \quad (2.2)$$

Where:

V = (ml of 0.1 N acid added)-(ml of 0.1 N NaOH used to neutralize the ammonia nitrogen)

W = weight of sample (g)

2.1.3 Ash content

An empty crucible was fire polished in a muffle furnace and allowed to cool in a desiccator for 20 minutes. Exactly 2 g of dried sample was weighed out into the crucible and transferred into the furnace at 650 °C for 3 hours. The crucible was brought out and put into the desiccators to cool down before it was reweighed to get the final weight. The ash content was calculated thus as follows:

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{x-y}{w} \times 100 \quad (2.3)$$

Where:

x = weight of crucible + ash

y = weight of crucible

w = weight of sample (g) before ashing.

2.1.4 Fat content

A 250 ml round bottom flask was washed and put in an oven at 60 °C for 25 minutes and then allowed to cool at room temperature before it was reweighed. Exactly 10 g of sample was weighed and wrapped in a thimble. This was inserted into an extraction column with a condenser connected. 200 ml of the extracting solvent (N- Hexane, boiling point 60-80 °C) was poured into the round bottom flask and fitted into the extraction unit. The flask was heated with the aid of electro thermal heater at 60 °C for 5 hours. After extraction, the thimble was removed and the solvent salvaged by distillation. The flask and its content were left in the oven overnight at a low temperature to completely evaporate the solvent and weighed to obtain the percentage fat content (AOAC, 2010).

$$\% \text{ fat content} = \frac{A-B}{C} \times 100 \quad (2.4)$$

Where:

A = Initial weight of Sample +thimble

B = Final weight of Sample + thimble

C = Initial weight of Sample.

2.1.5 Carbohydrate content

The total percentage carbohydrate content was determined by difference method. This involved addition of the total values of protein, fat, ash and moisture content and was subtracted from 100.

2.2 Chemical analysis

2.2.1 Acid value

Fifty (50) ml of mixture of diethyl ether and 95% ethanol was put into a conical flask. 1 ml phenolphthalein indication was added to neutralize the mixture with few drop of 0. 1 M NaOH. Exactly 2 g of sample was added to the neutralized mixture. It was titrated with 0.1 ml NaOH until a persistent pink colour was obtained (AOAC, 2010).

2.2.2 Iodine value

Twenty five (25) ml of Dams Bromide solution was shaken with 2 g of sample which was dissolved in 10 cm³ of Chloroforms in a conical flask place. The mixture was left in the dark for 30 minutes. 10 cm³ of 10% potassium iodide solution was added to the mixture and shaken thoroughly. The conical flask was washed with 75 ml of distilled water. 1 ml of starch indicator was added .The solution was titrated against 0.1 ml Na₂S₂O₃ until the end point was reached. A blank was prepared simultaneously (AOAC, 2010).

2.2.3 Saponification value

Exactly 2 g of sample was put into a conical flask; 25 ml of alcoholic potassium hydrate was pipette into the flask which was fitted with a reflux condenser on a hot water bath for 60 minute. 1 ml of Phenolphthalein indicator was added. It was titrated against the hot solution with 0.5 M HCl. A blank was also prepared into another flask simultaneously (AOAC, 2010).

2.2.4 Peroxide value

This work was carried out in subdue light. Exactly 2 g of sample was put into a conical flask with 2 g of powdered potassium iodide, 20 ml of the solution (glacial acetic acid/Chloroform (2:1%)) was added and the mixture was heated for 60 seconds. 20 ml of 5% potassium iodide solution was added to the heated mixture. 25 ml of distilled water was used to rinse the mouth of the conical flask and 1 ml of starch indication was added. The solution was added to 0.0002 M Na₂S₂O₃ until the end point was reached (AOAC, 2010).

2.3 Sensory Evaluation

Sensory evaluation was also carried out using 30 semi-skilled randomly selected judges (Komolafe and Arawande, 2010) to compare the mayonnaise produced using moringa with different constituents (Plate 3.3) with the one taken as standard. The sensory evaluation was based on colour, taste, flavor, appearance and overall acceptability. Each panelist's score was reflected on a 9-point hedonic scale ranging from 9 (like extremely) to 1 (dislike extremely) as described by Masen (1982).

2.4 Statistical Analysis

All data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistical Package for Science and Social Science (SPSS version 16). Means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test at 5% level of probability as described by Steel and Torrie (1980).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Proximate analysis of moringa seed flour and mayonnaise fortified with moringa seed flour

The seed had a high fat, fibre and protein contents. The fat content was 38.99% ± 0.10, which was comparable to some oil seeds such as rapeseed (37%), palm kernel (36%), mustard (35%), sunflower (32%), palm fruit (20%), cotton seed (13%) and soybean (23.5%) (Andualem and Gessesse, 2014). The protein content was 28.62% ± 0.28 which was higher than some proteinous plant sources such as that of *Telferia occidentalis* (7.0%) and *Amaranthus hybridus* var.1 and var.2

at 17.60% and 18.99% (Ekop, 2007) and compare favourably with Brebra seed (*Milletia ferruginea*) which has protein content of 29.7% as reported by Andualem and Gessesse (2014). The fibre content was 7.56% which was higher than the one reported (0.8 to 6.29%) for most tropical plant seeds in Africa (Ekop, 2007; Akubugwo *et al.*, 2007; Akpambang *et al.*, 2008). The moisture content for samples A to D showed that moisture content increased as the percentage of moringa seed flour added increased as shown in table 2. The reverse was the case for samples E-H, where the moisture content reduced as the percentage moringa seed flour added increased except for sample F. For samples I-L, there was a slight significance difference in their moisture content. There was not much change in the values obtained for their moisture content but when compared with sample M, the moisture contents was lower than that of sample M. The moisture content was lower than the one reported by Babajide and Olatunde (2010), 49.79% and the one reported by Gaonkar *et al.* (2010), 18.29%. It was also lower than the moisture content obtained by Mbah (2012) which was 6.78%. Lower moisture content indicated longer shelf-life and slower rate of deterioration.

Table 2. Proximate Composition of Moringa Seed Flour

S/NO	Proximate content	% Content*
1.	Moisture	5.10±0.28
2.	Fat	38.99±0.10
3.	Ash	3.83±0.12
4.	Protein	28.62±0.28
5.	Fibre	7.56±0.09
6	Carbohydrate	15.90±0.12

*Mean ±SD

There was significant difference between the samples ($P \leq 0.05$). There was an increase in the ash content increased as the quantity of moringa seed flour increased. Ogunsina *et al.* (2010) reported that powdered moringa seed had a high ash content of 43.58 g/100 g of sample. The ash content was lower than the ash content of moringa flour reported by Abiodun *et al.* (2012), but it fell within the range for full fat and low fat Mayonnaise (1.14-1.57) reported by Amin *et al.* (2014). Ash content of the samples with moringa was higher when compared with the ash content of the samples without moringa, as the quantity of moringa increased, the ash content also increased.

Protein content of the samples ranged between 0.14 and 0.42% (Table 3). Samples with 3% moringa seed flour had the highest protein value while sample M (mayonnaise bought from market) had the lowest protein content. There was an increase in the protein content of samples A to D (Table 3), the increase in protein content showed that there was a percentage increase in the protein content when compared with the control. Sample B had a percentage increase of 38% when compared with sample C, sample C had a percentage increase of 44.83% when compared with the control, sample D had a percentage increase of 62.07%. Samples E to H (Table 3), sample F had a percentage increase of 18.75% when compared to sample E, sample G had a percentage increase of 93.75% and sample H also had the same percentage increase as sample G when compared with sample E. Samples I to L

(Table 3), sample J had a percentage increase of 7.14% when compared with sample I, sample k had a percentage increase of 21.31% from sample I, while sample L had a percentage increase of 46.15%. There were significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in the samples I to L as shown in Table 3.

This might be due to the high percentage of fat present in the mayonnaise which reduces the protein content of the moringa as reported by Abiodun *et al.* (2012) which stated that moringa seed cake had higher values in the ash, crude fibre, protein and carbohydrate content, which was as a result of the displacement of oil from the seed flour thereby increasing other parameters.

Fat content of the samples A to M ranged between 38.42 and 92.63% (Table 3). There was significance difference ($P \leq 0.05$) between samples A to M as shown in Table 4. Sample M (mayonnaise bought from market) had the least fat content which was 34.82% while the other samples had higher fat content that fell within the range reported by Dupree and Savage, (2001); Worrasinchai *et al.* (2006) and Amin *et al.* (2014). The fat content of samples A-D increased as the percentage of moringa seed flour added increased.

Carbohydrate content of the samples fell within the range of 13.39 to 58.87% (Table 3). There was significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the result obtained for the carbohydrate content of the samples as shown in Table 3. The values were higher than that obtained by Amin *et al.* (2014) [1.54% - 2.4%] but lower than what was reported by Babajide and Olatunde (2010) [17.92% - 19.95%]. The high carbohydrate content might be due to the fortification of the mayonnaise with moringa seed flour which had carbohydrate content of 16.5 g/100 g as reported by Ogunsina *et al.* (2010) and 10.59% as reported by Abiodun *et al.* (2012).

3.2 Chemical Analysis of Mayonnaise Fortified with Moringa Seed Flour

Samples A to M had saponification values ranged between 50.49 and 196.35 mgKOH/g of oil (Table 4). There were significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in the results obtained for saponification value. Addition of moringa seed flour has minimal effect on the saponification value as shown in the result obtained when the result was compared based on using the same acidifier to prepare the samples. The 1% fortification the samples prepared using vinegar and lemon-vinegar showed an increase. Lalas and Tsaknis (2002) reported the saponification value of olive oil to be between 179.80 and 188 mgKOH/g, while moringa oil was between 186.32 and 199.32 mgKOH/g. The values obtained for some of the produced mayonnaise fell below these values. This might be due to the addition of moringa seed flour and also the addition of the acids in form of lemon and vinegar during preparation.

Acid value for samples ranged between 1.68 and 11.78 mgKOH/g oil (Table 4). There was a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between the acid values. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between samples B and I. The acid value of olive oil reported by Muhammed *et al.* (2013) was 4.53 mg KOH/ g, and this agreed with the value obtained for few samples. Iodine value for samples ranged between 30.87 and 112.47 g/100 g of oil (Table 4). There was significant

difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between the samples except for samples D, E, G and H, where there are no significant difference (Table 4). There was a reduction in the iodine level at 2% fortification and an increase at 3% fortification. This increase was notable in the sample prepared using lemon and vinegar. Thus gave an indication of the degree of unsaturation of the oils as higher iodine value was attributed to high level of unsaturation (Ikhuoria and Maliki, 2007; Muhammed *et al.*, 2013). The iodine value was a measure of the amount of unsaturated fatty acids in the oil, the higher the iodine value the greater the level of unsaturation and the higher the tendency for oxidation and polymerization to take place. The

peroxide values for samples fell within the range of 5.97 and 21.97 meqO₂/kg oil (Table 4). There was significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the samples except for samples A, G, B, C, I, J and L (Table 4), where there was no significant difference. The values obtained were lower than that of olive oil (17meqO₂/kg oil) reported by Muhammed *et al.* (2013), except for samples E and K (Table 4). Najafi *et al.* (2015) reported that processed oil should not exceed 15 meqO₂/kg oil, and processing decreased the peroxide level. Peroxide value is associated with the rancidity of the oil and is the measure of primary oxidation (Muco *et al.*, 2015).

Table 3. Proximate Composition of mayonnaise fortified with moringa Seed flour

Samples	M.C (%)	A.C (%)	F.C (%)	P.C (%)	CHO (%)
A	2.35±0.006a	0.68±0.006a	83.17±0.758f	0.29±0.006f	13.51±0.064c
B	2.90±0.006e	1.01±0.006e	82.65±0.006f	0.40±0.006h	13.04±0.600c
C	3.65±0.006f	1.23±0.006i	92.63±5.768h	0.42±0.006i	2.07±0.000b
D	5.30±0.006k	1.59±0.006k	92.63±5.768h	0.47±0.006j	0.01±0.829a
E	3.86±0.006h	0.79±0.006c	86.65±0.006g	0.16±0.006b	8.54±0.012b
F	4.40±0.006j	0.96±0.006d	64.27±0.006d	0.19±0.006d	30.18±0.012g
G	3.69±0.006g	1.05±0.006f	68.08±0.006e	0.31±0.006g	26.87±0.012f
H	2.45±0.006b	1.15±0.006h	54.47±0.058b	0.31±0.006g	41.62±0.0064i
I	2.74±0.006d	0.75±0.006b	58.87±0.058c	0.14±0.006a	37.50±0.052h
J	2.74±0.006d	1.10±0.006g	69.47±0.058c	0.15±0.006a	26.55±0.075f
K	2.70±0.006c	1.24±0.006j	81.58±0.006f	0.17±0.006c	14.31±0.012d
L	2.75±0.006d	1.05±0.006f	70.20±0.006e	0.26±0.006e	25.74±0.012e
M	4.37±0.006i	1.80±0.006l	34.82±0.006a	0.14±0.006a	58.87±0.000j

Mean within the same column with different alphabets are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

A =Mayonnaise made with lemon juice, B = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, C = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, D = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, E = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar, F = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar+ 1% moringa seed flour, G = Mayonnaise made with vinegar + 2% moringa seed flour, H = Mayonnaise made with vinegar+ 3% moringa seed flour, I = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice, J = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, K = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, L = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, M = Mayonnaise bought from market(Extreme Mayonnaise)

M.C= Moisture content, P.C= Protein content, A.C= Ash content, F.C= Fat content, CHO= Carbohydrate content

The pH of samples ranged between 3.40 and 5.57 (Table 4). Sample M had the least pH value of (3.40). This might be due to other additional additives as part of the constituent of the sample M. The quantity of moringa seed flour did not have any effect on the pH level of the mayonnaise. The higher pH values of the produced mayonnaise might be due to the addition of egg yolk which has a pH of 6 as reported by Hui *et al.* (2009) and Blitz *et al.* (2009). The pH level increased with increased in fat content and this might be due to dilution of the acid by the fat (Amin *et al.*, 2014).

There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between samples C, D, E, F, H and M. There was slight significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in samples B and I (Table 4); samples A, G, J, K, and L.

Sensory Evaluation of Mayonnaise fortified with Moringa Seed flour

The results of the sensory evaluation of the fortified mayonnaise are as indicated in Table 5. Appearance of sample A to M ranged between 3.87 and d 6.57. There was no significant difference in sample B and sample M, while samples A to D had significant difference in appearance (Table 5). There was slight significant difference between samples E, F, G, and M (Table 5). There was significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in samples A and G, while there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in samples D and L; B and E;

F, and J. There were slight significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in samples C and M (Table 5). Table 5 showed that samples A, E and I had higher frequencies of 7.0 which was very desirable, while samples B, F, J, and M had the frequencies of 6.0 which was slightly desirable, Samples D, H and L were the least desired in all the samples in terms of appearance. The result obtained was in agreement of with the reports of Santos *et al.* (2009) and Ogbe and Affiku (2011).

The values obtained for colour of samples A to M ranged between 3.70-6.27. The result showed that there was slight significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 5) in 5 samples A, B, E, F, I, J and M, samples C, G, and K, samples D, H and L. According to Rasool *et al.* (2013) and Abu-Salem and Abou-arab (2008), colour was an important factor that affect the value of any food product especially mayonnaise. It was an important factor in consumer's acceptability.

Samples A, B, E, F, I, J and M had the generally accepted colour that is off- white colour. They still retained the colour of the egg that had been whisked with oil. Table 5 showed that sample D was the least accepted in terms of colour while sample G was the least accepted and sample L.

Table 5 showed the level of brightness of the colour of the mayonnaise with samples A, E, I and M had the highest frequencies for brightness, while samples H and L had the least brightness in terms of colour.

The values for flavor of samples A to M ranged between 3.53 and 6.20. There was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in sample D. There was slight significant difference ($p\leq 0.05$) in samples A (Table 5), E (Table 5), I (Table 5), and J, samples B and F, samples C and K, samples G, and M, samples H and L. The flavors of the other samples except for sample D were acceptable (Table 5).

Table 5 showed that samples A and I, were liked very much, samples C, D, H, K, L, and M are moderately liked while sample D was the least liked.

The values for taste of samples A to M range from 3.83-6.23. There was no significant difference ($p\leq 0.05$) in sample D (Table 5), there was slight difference ($p>0.05$) (Table 5) in samples A and I, samples B, E, F and J, samples C and M, samples C and K, samples H and L.

The taste of all the samples except for sample D was acceptable. Samples D, H and L were least accepted. Sample

A and E were the most liked in term of taste while samples D, H and L were the least liked.

The values for texture of samples A to M ranges from 2.57 to 4.27. There was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in sample D (Table 5), there was slight significance difference ($p\leq 0.05$) samples A, I, and M, samples G, and J. Sample A, E, I, and M were smooth while samples H and K were coarse.

The overall acceptability for the samples A to M ranged from 3.90 to 6.20. There was significant difference ($p\leq 0.05$) in samples D (Table 5), H and L, samples C, G, K and M, while there was slight significant difference ($p\leq 0.05$) in samples B, E, I, J and also sample F.

Sample A and I, had the highest value of acceptance followed by samples B, E, and J. Samples A, B, F, G, J, M were generally acceptable, while samples D and H were the least generally acceptable.

Table 4. Chemical properties of mayonnaise fortified with moringa Seed flour

Samples	S.V(mg KOH/g oil)	A.V(mg KOH/g Oil)	I.V(g/100g Oil)	P.V (meq O ₂ / Kg Oil)	pH
A	131.84±0.006a	1.68±0.006a	70.91±0.000e	11.97±0.033a	5.14±0.010d
B	129.03±0.006g	3.37±0.006b	80.13±0.000g	7.67±0.577e	5.33±0.010f
C	145.86±0.006i	7.83±0.006i	30.87±0.006a	7.67±0.577e	5.57±0.010h
D	145.86±0.006i	6.73±0.006g	80.50±0.000i	6.67±0.577c	5.68±0.010i
E	50.49±0.006a	6.17±0.006f	80.52±0.289i	23.97±0.058j	5.03±0.010b
F	176.72±0.006j	4.49±0.000c	80.02±0.010f	15.97±0.058h	5.47±0.010g
G	61.71±0.006b	7.29±0.006h	70.29±0.289d	3.97±0.058a	5.08±0.010c
H	92.57±0.006e	8.42±0.006j	70.29±0.017d	5.97±0.058b	5.27±0.010e
I	86.96±0.006c	3.37±0.006b	80.15±0.000g	7.97±0.058e	5.34±0.010f
J	95.37±0.006f	6.17±0.006f	60.81±0.000c	9.97±0.058e	5.09±0.010cd
K	92.76±0.006e	11.78±0.006k	50.52±0.000b	21.97±0.058i	5.09±0.010cd
L	89.76±0.006d	5.05±0.006d	80.42±0.092h	7.97±0.058e	5.11±0.010cd
M	196.35±0.006k	5.39±0.006e	112.47±0.058j	7.17±0.058c	3.40±0.100a

Mean within the same column with different alphabets are significantly different ($p\leq 0.05$)

A =Mayonnaise made with lemon juice, B = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, C = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, D = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, E = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar, F = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar+ 1% moringa seed flour, G = Mayonnaise made with vinegar + 2% moringa seed flour, H = Mayonnaise made with vinegar+ 3% moringa seed flour, I = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice, J = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, K = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, L = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, M = Mayonnaise bought from market. S.V= Saponification Value, A.V= Acid Value, P.V= Peroxide Value, I.V= Iodine Value

Table 5. Sensory Evaluation of mayonnaise Fortified with moringa Seed Flour

Sample	Appearance	Colour	Flavour	Taste	Texture	Overall acceptability
A	6.57±0.568d	6.27±0.740c	6.20±1.127e	6.23±1.073e	2.77±2.417a	6.20±0.847d
B	5.83±1.147ef	5.60±0.770c	5.47±1.252d	5.60±1.276de	3.40±1.831abc	5.70±0.784cd
C	4.77±1.330bc	4.73±1.258b	4.67±1.372bc	4.87±1.137cd	3.37±1.564abc	4.83±1.392b
D	3.93±1.461a	3.70±1.489a	3.53±1.479a	3.57±1.479a	4.27±1.701c	3.90±1.605a
E	5.83±1.262ef	6.13±0.937c	5.80±1.157e	5.63±1.474de	2.80±1.937a	5.90±1.242cd
F	5.17±1.085cde	5.60±0.932c	5.50±1.358d	5.53±0.937de	3.63±1.810abc	5.43±1.048bc
G	4.83±0.986c	4.80±0.997b	4.93±1.311cd	4.43±1.431bc	3.17±1.392ab	4.87±1.358b
H	4.13±1.502ab	3.87±1.252a	4.07±1.413ab	4.07±1.847bc	4.03±1.847bc	3.93±1.461a
I	6.13±1.106fg	6.20±1.157c	6.00±1.017e	5.80±1.324e	2.57±1.942a	6.13±1.408cd
J	5.40±1.192cde	5.70±1.022c	5.70±1.022c	5.60±1.133de	3.00±1.554ab	5.80±1.095cd
K	5.03±1.159cd	4.77±1.430b	4.53±1.306bc	4.47±1.592bc	3.63±1.752abc	4.80±1.375b
L	3.87±1.655a	3.87±1.43a	4.10±1.605ab	3.83±1.533ab	4.03±1.847bc	4.10±1.561a
M	5.70±1.512def	5.93±1.23c	4.90±1.826cd	4.87±1.814cd	2.77±2.144a	4.90±1.749b

Mean within the same column with different alphabets are significantly different ($p\leq 0.05$)

A =Mayonnaise made with lemon juice, B = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, C = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, D = Mayonnaise made with lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, E = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar, F = Mayonnaise made with Vinegar+ 1% moringa seed flour, G = Mayonnaise made with vinegar + 2% moringa seed flour, H = Mayonnaise made with vinegar+ 3% moringa seed flour, I = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice, J = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 1% moringa seed flour, K = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 2% moringa seed flour, L = Mayonnaise made with vinegar and lemon juice+ 3% moringa seed flour, M = Mayonnaise bought from market

IV. CONCLUSION

The chemical composition of the moringa seed flour and mayonnaise fortified with moringa seed flour were observed

to vary. The mayonnaise produced was nutritious and generally accepted. The proximate analysis results showed that as the percentage increase in the quantity of moringa seed

flour added to the mayonnaise, there were high percentage increases in the level of protein and ash contents.

The Chemical analysis showed that at 1% moringa seed flour fortification of the mayonnaise, the acid value was low and the peroxide value was still within the safe level and rancidity had not started. The sensory evaluation showed that the mayonnaise fortified with 1% moringa seed flour was accepted in terms of all the parameters tested for: colour, taste, texture, flavor, appearance and general acceptability.

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